

Deliverable 6.6

PRACTICE ABSTRACTS - BATCH 2

Practice abstracts – batch 2

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Table of Contents

1	INTRODUCTION	8
1.1	<i>Common Format.....</i>	8
1.1.1	Obligatory elements.....	8
1.1.2	Recommended elements.....	9
1.1.3	Optional elements.....	9
1.2	<i>Common format excel file.....</i>	9
1.3	<i>Structure and Content of Practice Abstracts.....</i>	11
2	Project Objectives.....	13
3	Practice abstracts (Batch 2).....	14
3.1	<i>Practice Abstract 6</i>	14
3.2	<i>Practice Abstract 7</i>	14
3.3	<i>Practice Abstract 8</i>	15
3.4	<i>Practice Abstract 9</i>	15
3.5	<i>Practice Abstract 10.....</i>	16
4	Conclusion	17

List of figures

Figure 1	Project Identification	9
Figure 2	Project Information	10
Figure 3	Contact partners.....	10
Figure 4	Keywords	10
Figure 5	Websites	11
Figure 6	Audiovisual Material.....	11
Figure 7	Structure and content of Practice Abstract 2nd batch	12

Glossary of terms and acronyms

Acronym/Term	Description
CS	Case Study
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
EIP-AGRI	European Innovation Partnership Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
FIC	Food Information to Consumers
FLW	Food Loss & Waste
FW	Food Waste
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
PA	Practice Abstract
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This document constitutes the deliverable D6.6 Project Abstract -batch 2 of the CHORIZO project and has been prepared by **FIAB**. This document corresponds to the second deliverable of two that presents the second batch of five Project Abstracts developed with results obtained during the project.

A “practice abstract” is a short summary which describes a main information/recommendation/practice that can be used by the end-users in their daily practice. Projects can share their intermediate and final results through practice abstracts. A total target number of 10 practice abstracts have been foreseen for the project. These include practice abstracts based on CHORIZO results or activities with a particular focus on the inputs from the remaining Case Studies and the tools developed within the project to enhance the impact of the results — namely, the Datahub, the FLW Rapid Appraisal Tool, and the sector-specific capacity building programme

The resulting innovative knowledge from this project is fed into the European Innovation Partnership Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) website for broad dissemination to practitioners. End-user material has been produced in the form of a number of summaries for practitioners in the EIP common format ("practice abstracts"). The project details were submitted to the platform with the submission of this first batch deliverable. Guidance and template used for the development of these practice abstracts were downloaded from the new [EIP-AGRI website](#).

The EIP common format consists of a set of basic elements characterising the project and includes one or more "practice abstract(s)". The format was developed with two main objectives:

- (1) to make it possible to contact project partners and encourage knowledge exchange
- (2) to disseminate the results of the project in a concise and easy understandable way to practitioners.

The success and impact of an innovative project depends strongly on its communication, and

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Common Format

End-user material has been produced in the form of a number of summaries for practitioners in the EIP common format ("practice abstracts"). The common format allows providing information all along the life-cycle of the project. The common format consists in obligatory, recommended and optional elements. Its fields are listed in the bullets below.

1.1.1 Obligatory elements

- **Title of the project in native language:** short and easily understandable (one key sentence on the project; max 150 characters, word count – with spaces).
- **Title of the project in English:** short and easily understandable (one key sentence on the project; max 150 characters, word count – no spaces).
- **Editor of the text:** person/organisation responsible for delivering the text.
- **Project coordinator** (lead-partner) according to the cooperation/consortium agreement: name, address, e-mail, telephone.
- **Project partners:** name, address, e-mail, telephone, type of partner (farm holder, advisor, research institute, SME, NGO, or other).
- **Keyword-category** (to be chosen from a pre-defined list of categories).
- **Project period** (starting date, end date).
- **Project status:** ongoing (after selection of the project) or completed (after final payment).
- **Main funding source** (Rural development programme, H2020, or other EU, national/regional or private funds).
- **Total budget** of the project.
- **Geographical location where the main project activities take place:** NUTS 3 level, to enable contacting within/between a climatic/regional entities.
- **Final report** (in the form of an annex), including a substantial description of the results - obligatory once the project is completed – to be drafted according to the requirements specific for the funding source.

Practice abstract should contain:

- **Objective of the project:** what problems/opportunities does the project address that are relevant for the practitioner/end-user, and how will they be solved? - (300-600 characters, word count – no spaces).
- **Short summary for practitioners** on the (final or expected) outcomes (1000-1500 characters, word count – no spaces). This summary should at least contain the following information:

- Main results/outcomes of the activity (expected or final)
- The main practical recommendation(s): what would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented? How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This summary should be as interesting as possible for end-users, using a direct and easy understandable language and pointing out to practical findings which are particularly relevant for practitioners (e.g. related to cost, productivity etc). Research oriented aspects which do not help the understanding of the practice itself should be avoided.

1.1.2 Recommended elements

- **Description of project activities:** (max 600 characters, word count – no spaces): short summary highlighting main project activities.
- **Short summary for practitioners:** short summary according to guidance (see box above; 1000-1500 characters - no spaces)
- **Audiovisual material** which is useful and attractive for practitioners (e.g. YouTube link, videos, other dissemination material).
- **Website** of the project (URL)
- **Links to other website(s)** hosting information on the project (results) that are available after the project has ended, by preference using the existing local/regional/national communication channels that practitioners most often use.

1.1.3 Optional elements

- **Description of the context of the project** (e.g. drivers in legislation/markets or other causes that were at the origin of the project, etc.)
- **Additional information on the project** as required by the specific guidance at national/regional level (e.g. for detailed monitoring purposes)
- **Additional comments:** free text field which can be used by the editor e.g. for listing facilitating elements or obstacles for the implementation of the produced results, for suggestions for future actions/research, for messages to consumers, etc.

1.2 Common format Excel file

A template for Practice Abstracts with a common format was filled out and the following pictures show the main sections.

Figure 1 Project Identification

	A	B	C	D
34	Objective of the project in English: what problems/opportunities does the project address that are relevant for the practitioner/end-user, and how will they be solved? - (300-600 characters, word count – no spaces)	The project aims to improve the understanding of how social norms influence behavior related to food loss and waste (FLW) generation. Then use this knowledge to improve the effectiveness of the strategies that must be followed to achieve zero waste. CHORIZO employs real-life Case Studies (CSs) to provide information and data on the context and impact of previous FLW prevention/reduction actions undertaken by the Case Study members, thus enriching the evidence-based analysis on previous FLW actions.	Mandatory	430 character(s) / 600
35	Objective of the project in native language: (can be the language of the coordinator / one of the partners - otherwise indicate "see objectives in English") (300-600 characters, word count – no spaces)	The project aims to improve the understanding of how social norms influence behavior related to food loss and waste (FLW) generation. Then use this knowledge to improve the effectiveness of the strategies that must be followed to achieve zero waste. CHORIZO employs real-life Case Studies (CSs) to provide information and data on the context and impact of previous FLW prevention/reduction actions undertaken by the Case Study members, thus enriching the evidence-based analysis on previous FLW actions.	Mandatory	430 character(s) / 600
36	Description of project activities in English: (max 600 characters, word count – no spaces): short summary highlighting main project activities.	The project is divided in Work Packages (WPs) to organize the work between the partners: (1) Evidence based analysis and sector specific guidance; (2) Empirical Datahub with 6 different Case Studies; (3) Predictive analytics and modelling backbone for changing social norms towards 0FLW; (4) Actor, context and gender specific change fostering; (5) Innovation upscaling; (6) Dissemination, Exploitation and communication; (7) project management and (8) Ethics requirements.	Recommended	408 character(s) / 600

< > ... INSTRUCTIONS PRIVACY IDENTIFICATION **PROJECT INFORMATION** PARTNERS AUDIOVISUAL MATERIAL KEYWORDS

Figure 2 Project Information

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Project partners (mandatory information) - N.B. : "Name" can be that of the Organisation or of a contact person - "Address" should include the country						
2		Name	Address	E-mail	Telephone	Type of partner	Consent for publication
3	project coordinator (lead partner) from PROJECT INFORMATION	EV ILVO (EIGEN VERMOGEN)	BURG. VAN GANSBERGHELAAR	fleur.marchand@ilvo.vlaanderen.be	+32486335644	research institute	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
4	project partner	FEDERACION DE INDUSTRIAS	SPAIN	c.avila@fiab.es	(+34) 648819161	other	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes
5	project partner	FEDERACION DE INDUSTRIAS	SPAIN	g.alcat@fiab.es	(+34) 610269115	other	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes
6	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
7	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
8	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
9	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
10	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
11	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
12	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
13	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
14	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
15	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
16	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
17	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
18	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
19	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes
20	project partner						<input type="checkbox"/> Yes

< > ... PRIVACY IDENTIFICATION **PARTNERS** AUDIOVISUAL MATERIAL KEYWORDS WEBSITES PA1 PA2 PA3 PA4 PA5 PA6 PA7

Figure 3 Contact partners

	A	B	C
1	Keyword - category		
2	Keyword - category 1	Waste, by-products and residues management	Mandatory
3	Keyword - category 2		Optional
4	Keyword - category 3		Optional
5	Keyword - category 4		Optional
6	Keyword - category 5		Optional
7	Keyword - category 6		Optional
8	Keyword - category 7		Optional
9	Keyword - category 8		Optional
10	Keyword - category 9		Optional
11	Keyword - category 10		Optional
12			
13			

Figure 4 Keywords

A	B	C	D
1	Official website of the project	Recommended	
2	Title/description	URL	Additional comments
3	CHORIZO project website	https://chorizoproject.eu/	
4	Links to other website(s) hosting information on the project (results) that are available after the project has ended, by preference using the existing local/regional/national communication channels that practitioners most often use.		Recommended
5	Title/description	URL	Additional comments
6	Data hub	https://data.chorizoproject.eu/	Repository for project results and inputs
7		http://	
8		http://	
9		http://	
10		http://	

Figure 5 Websites

A	B	C	D
1	Audiovisual material which is useful and attractive for practitioners (e.g. YouTube link, videos, other dissemination material)	Recommended	
2	Title/description (in English)	URL	Additional comments
3	Deliverable 1.4 Sector-Specific guidance	https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/CHORIZO-D1.4-Sector-Specific-Guidance.pdf	
4	Deliverable 2.1 Case Studies Strategic Plan	https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/D2.1_Case-Studies-Strategic-Plan.pdf	
5	CHORIZO Twitter account	https://twitter.com/CHORIZOproject	
6	CHORIZO LinkedIn account	https://www.linkedin.com/company/chorizoproject/	
7	CHORIZO YouTube account	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UckVWnjslzWZyYCEg5wng4A	
8	CHORIZO Leaflet	https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/CHORIZO-FOLLETO_web.pdf	
9	CHORIZO dissemination material	https://chorizoproject.eu/dissemination_and_newsletter/	
10	Practice Abstract 1	http://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/CHORIZO	Short version of PA1
11	Practice Abstract 2	https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/CHORIZO	Short version of PA2
12	Practice Abstract 3	https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/CHORIZO	Short version of PA3
13	Practice Abstract 4	https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/CHORIZO	Long version of PA4
14	Practice Abstract 5	https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/CHORIZO	Short version of PA5
15	Practice Abstract 6	https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/PRACTIC	Short version of PA6
16	Practice Abstract 7	https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/PRACTIC	Short version of PA7
17	Practice Abstract 8	https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/PRACTIC	Short version of PA8
18	Practice Abstract 9	https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/PRACTIC	Short version of PA9
19	Practice Abstract 10	https://chorizoproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/07/PRACTIC	Short version of PA10
20		http://	
21		http://	
22		http://	

Figure 6 Audiovisual Material

1.3 Structure and Content of Practice Abstracts

The project aims to generate credible and sustainable scientific, societal and economic/technological impacts. The development of a sector-specific guidance on actions that address food loss and food waste was one of the main activities developed during the project. Some of the new five Practice Abstracts are focussed on the lessons learnt from past and current FLW prevention actions and will serve as a main guidance per sector to support different types of actors from the food system to design and decide on their efforts towards zero FLW. Since “practice abstracts” are short summaries which describe a main information/ recommendation/ practice that can be used by end-users in their daily practice, in particular, Hospitality sector and Food Industry are the two topics covered. The content of the other 3 practice abstracts focuses on presenting the tools developed within the project to enhance the impact of the results — namely, the Datahub, the FLW Rapid Appraisal Tool, and the sector-specific capacity building programme.

The final structure and partners involved are shown in the table below. The following table contains the topic and target group of practitioners, the material that the core group proposes to consult for writing the PA, the partners involved and the “guardian” (understood as person who guards the general storyline of the PA).

	TOPIC and targeted group of practitioners	Materials to consult for writing the PA	Content deliverers	'Guardian' of the storyline
6	FLW in hospitality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CS2 hospitality D1.4 chapters 3.5 (food services) 	Strawberry	FIAB
7	FLW in food industry related to date marking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CS6 packaging (industry part) 	FIAB	INLECOM
8	DataHub – “Insighter”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP2 CHORIZO FLW ‘Insighter’ datahub WP5 Upscaling Strategy 	ILVO INLECOM	CSCP
9	FLW Rapid Appraisal Tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is for? How to use it? 	UNIBO	ILVO
10	Capacity Building Program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WP4: to support the uptake of sector-specific guidance of CHORIZO 	CSCP	FIAB

Figure 7 Structure and content of Practice Abstract 2nd batch

2 PROJECT OBJECTIVES

To properly understand the Project Abstracts developed during the project, it is first necessary to recall the objectives and the aim of the CHORIZO project. In this essence, CHORIZO is a project funded by Horizon Europe programme that aims to improve the understanding between social norms, consumer behaviours and economic actor decisions and Food Loss and Waste generation and use this knowledge to improve the effectiveness of decision-making and engagement of food chain actors, towards zero food waste. The project's main goal is to address existing research gaps and use its outcomes to deliver and advance innovations, helping relevant actors to be engaged more effectively in food waste prevention and reduction activities. In short, it is a European project that integrates different food chain actors to enhance contingency knowledge and produce new effective instruments for facilitating successful transitions towards minimising FLW.

To achieve its aim, the project provides evidence on the role of existing social norms in actors' FLW behaviours through translating results from previous FLW actions into evidence and generate new evidence on social norms & FLW behaviours. Second, CHORIZO embeds these research results into innovation products that can foster change of FLW-related social norms. These products include a sector-specific guidance, communication & science education packages and capacity building actions. CHORIZO employs real-life Case Studies (CSs) to serve the above-mentioned purposes. The aim of practice abstracts is to share those project outputs so other actors of the agri-food sector can leverage on them and to see the main added value and benefits met by the end-users if the generated knowledge is implemented.

3 PRACTICE ABSTRACTS (BATCH 2)

The resulting innovative knowledge from this project is [uploaded into the EIP-AGRI website](#) for broad dissemination to practitioners. The second batch includes end-user material produced in the form of a number of summaries for practitioners in the EIP common format. The following abstracts were submitted (from PA 6 to PA 10):

3.1 Practice Abstract 6

Shrot Title (150 characters): Influence of social norms on food waste behavior in hospitality.

Short summary for practitioners (1000-1500 characters):

CHORIZO explores how social norms influence food waste (FW) behavior. A Norwegian hotel chain examined: (1) how communication tone (none vs positive vs provocative) impacts FW at breakfast buffets, (2) the effect of staff education on food production and procurement, and (3) differences in consumer FW between buffet and plated lunches at conferences.

Key findings:

- Communication signs affect guest behaviour. The “Breakfast Experiment” showed that positive messages reduced FW, while provocative ones increased it—especially among leisure guests. Business travellers were less influenced. Messaging must be tailored to guest profiles.
- Chefs’ training and background influence how food is served, prepared, and wasted. Certified chefs showed more structure and responsibility. Language barriers challenged communication for some chefs. While there were no formal FW routines, implicit norms, quality control and reuse of leftovers (e.g., in staff meals) were common practice. Permissive norms allowed flexibility in handling surplus.
- Buffet and plated service both have pros and cons. Buffets lead to guest-driven waste; plated meals risk portion miscalculation. Daily FW varied, showing the complexity of waste generation and the need for oversight throughout the food service chain.

Guest communication significantly affects FW and must be used wisely. Provocative messages can increase waste, while positive messages reduce it. Both serving styles have pros and cons: both need to be optimized. Staff training, operational control, and careful balancing of serving styles are crucial to minimizing food waste.

3.2 Practice Abstract 7

Shrot Title (150 characters): Smart Packaging and Date Marking: Integrated Strategies to Reduce Food Waste.

Short summary for practitioners (1000-1500 characters):

According to the FAO (2024), food losses occur at various stages, including handling and storage (12%), processing (5%), and distribution and marketing (9%). Up to 10% of Food Waste (FW) in the EU is linked to date marking, the confusion surrounding "use by" and "best before" labels often leads consumers to discard food prematurely.

Food industries work under strict rules and laws about food safety, they apply the FIC Regulation with respect to date marks. Nevertheless, many companies recall being influenced by external factors, such as consumer preferences, consumer storage behaviour or the requirements from RETAIL.

It is therefore crucial to understand the role of date marking in FW and study how sustainable and smart packaging can mitigate food waste. Findings highlight that a lack of consumer understanding of expiration dates leads to increased food disposal habits. Furthermore, while smart packaging offers potential benefits, such as extended shelf life and improved food preservation, increase of prices and consumer resistance remains a challenge. Many are unwilling to pay more for these innovations, despite their long-term sustainability benefits. Provide clear information in labels, educate consumers for preserving products and inform about improvements in packaging is vital to induce informed choices taken by consumers and could avoid big amounts of FW. In this context, the influence that the food industry has on consumer behaviour is bigger than expected.

By enhancing awareness and changing behavioural patterns, this study emphasizes the importance of a collaborative approach between consumers, industry, and policymakers to minimize food waste effectively.

3.3 Practice Abstract 8

Shrot Title (150 characters): **Chorizo FLW Datahub and “Insighter”:** **Supporting intervention design towards Zero Food Waste.**

Short summary for practitioners (1000-1500 characters):

Effectively addressing the global challenge of food loss and waste (FLW) requires more than technological fixes; it demands a deeper understanding of social behaviours and norms that influence food-related practices. The CHORIZO project aims to support food system stakeholders in designing targeted, evidence-based interventions that consider how social norms shape behaviours around FLW.

To this end, CHORIZO provides the FLW Datahub and “Insighter.” The datahub is a central platform storing and providing easy access to empirical data from case studies (surveys, in depth interviews, and experiments) and more about 400 FLW actions in diverse sectors. About half of these actions focus on FLW prevention strategies, the other half tackles aspects of food waste reduction such as re-use and recycling of food. The datahub also provides educational materials and communication resources relevant to promote long-term behavioural shifts.

The “Insighter” helps stakeholders assess the potential impact of FW strategies by sharing findings on simulated interventions and exploring behaviour change scenarios generated in the project. This builds upon evidence from empirical and simulated data from CHORIZO case studies and leverages the use of behavioural modelling and predictive analytics.

In conclusion, the datahub and “Insighter” combines data, behavioural insights, and digital innovation to provide researchers, NGOs, food banks, households, food service providers, and educational institutions with a scalable, adaptable framework to drive collective action toward zero food waste across the EU and beyond.

3.4 Practice Abstract 9

Shrot Title (150 characters): **Food Waste Rapid Appraisal Tool: A Streamlined and Visually Supported Instrument to Identify Food Waste Drivers.**

Short summary for practitioners (1000-1500 characters):

The Food Waste Rapid Appraisal Tool is an easy-to-use, interactive web-based simulator developed as part of the Horizon Europe CHORIZO project. It helps users make informed decisions to reduce

food waste by simulating real-world behaviours and environments. The tool includes two behaviourally grounded models:

- The Establishment Diner model, which simulates food choices and waste behaviours in buffet-style hospitality settings.
- The Home Cook model, which focuses on food waste dynamics in households, including storage, purchasing, and consumption strategies.

Users can explore 49 ready-made scenarios - 37 for hospitality and 12 for households. Each scenario combines key behavioural and contextual factors like plate size, guest composition, sustainability awareness, communication framing, consumption strategies and eating preferences. The tool shows the average food waste amount per guest or household, along with clear, plain-language insights and tailored recommendations.

Designed for policy actors, food service professionals, and researchers, the tool allows users to compare different behavioural scenarios, identify effective interventions, and support capacity building. It highlights how individual motivations, social norms, and structural factors interact to influence food waste outcomes. The tool requires no technical skills, is accessible online, and supports rapid, informed appraisal of food waste prevention strategies across a wide range of settings.

3.5 Practice Abstract 10

Shrot Title (150 characters): **Enriching food waste interventions with social norm insights.**

Short summary for practitioners (1000-1500 characters):

Social norms—unwritten rules shaping daily behaviour—play a key role for food waste creation. Recognizing their influence, CHORIZO developed a practical capacity-building programme and an easy-to-use guidance to help food chain actors design effective, norm-based interventions to foster food waste prevention and reduction in their sector. At its core is the “6+2 step approach,” which expands common behaviour change intervention planning with two crucial steps that focus specifically on social norms.

The 8 steps include: (1) define your objective, (2) understand your target group, (3) determine relevant social norms—are they descriptive (what people do) or injunctive (what people feel they should do)?, (4) choose the right approach —do you want to strengthen, change, or create a norm?, (5) plan the intervention, (6) do a reality check, (7) implement, and (8) evaluate the impact.

This CHORIZO approach equips practitioners with a strategy to create targeted, norm-informed actions that tap into existing behaviors or build new habits, making food waste interventions more effective. For those new to food waste reduction, all eight steps offer a clear roadmap to design impactful actions. For experienced professionals, the two social norm-focused steps provide valuable tools to enrich and enhance current practice.

Being aware of and actively shaping social norms can boost engagement, improve uptake, and lead to lasting reductions in food waste from farm to fork.

4 CONCLUSION

This second batch of Practice Abstracts strengthens CHORIZO's mission to deliver tangible and applicable results for diverse food system actors. By combining sector-specific recommendations for hospitality and the food industry with innovative tools for data, like the rapid appraisal, the datahub or the capacity building, these abstracts provide an integrated framework to support effective food loss and waste prevention. Together, they capture key lessons learned and practical solutions, contributing to lasting scientific, societal and economic impacts while advancing towards the common goal of zero food loss and waste.

Moreover, their open access availability through the EIP-AGRI website further increases their value, ensuring wide dissemination and accessibility. This not only enhances their immediate practical impact but also establishes a valuable knowledge base that can inspire and inform future research initiatives and projects in the field of food loss and waste reduction.

CHORIZO PROJECT

